

TECHNOLOGY OF USING COMMUNICATION EXERCISES TO DEVELOP READING SKILLS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSON

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ABSTRACT

The focus of the article is on the use of technology in communicative activities for teaching reading, which aids in the development and improvement of students' reading comprehension skills as well as their ability to work with texts of various genres. Frequent use of this technology-enabled literature helps you not only improve your reading comprehension but also get to the meaning level of the text. The writers suggested and examined a variety of communication exercises meant to be used with different kinds of texts and foster both reading comprehension and well-crafted speech statements that convey the author's own viewpoint.

Key words: *comprehension, functions; reading; skills and abilities; types of reading; technology; communication exercises; exposition; meaningful identification; meaningful search.*

Although several academics have given different definitions of reading, they all concur that reading is an active rather than passive activity. According to Rumelhart (1979), reading is a process that incorporates the reader, the text, and their interactions with each other. The reader must actively interpret the text in order to deduce its meaning; it is not there for them to passively absorb. According to Buck (1979) and Goodman (1984), reading is the universal act of interpreting written or printed symbols in order to make sense of them in many situations and languages.

Humans could not have formed or existed without communication. The process and outcome of forming connections between individuals, which serves numerous purposes, is communication. To put it more simply, these are the objectives that a person seeks throughout his social life and the problems that he resolves through dialogue. A reader's goal in trying to understand is just as great as a writer's potential communication goal. In this sense, "interpreting" can take the place of the term "reading."

According to Grabe & Stoller (2002), reading is connected to a number of important processes. They clarify that reading needs to happen quickly and with the effective execution of certain procedures. As the reader engages with the text and builds his perception of it using language and prior knowledge, reading is an interactive process. The reader then needs to be strategic, integrating a variety of particular abilities necessary for understanding. A reader needs to have a reason for reading, and this reason might motivate him to read. He needs to read adaptably to the evolving goals and the continuous observation. He has to assess if the reading's content aligns with his goal for reading in the interim. Reading is a process that combines both comprehension and learning since it allows the reader to absorb new knowledge. Lastly, in order to understand the meaning, the reader must use the linguistic elements of the text. To put it briefly, reading is an interactive process that includes the reader, the text, and the reader-text interaction. The two main parts of the reading process are typically understood to be decoding and comprehension, which entail language abilities and interpreting this understanding in light of the reader's prior knowledge.

Coordination (helping people coordinate joint actions); emotive (making you experience the emotions necessary for a full life); self-expression (a means of revealing one's essence); and socialization (a process through which a person learns to follow generally accepted normative standards) are just a few of the many functions that communication performs [Drozdova,2014].

Nonetheless, reading and listening are examples of receptive behaviors that fall under the purview of communication functions. In this instance, the person tries to meet his wants by influencing oneself through a book, essay, or reference material rather than his speech partner:

- get new knowledge; - make the info more clear;
- gather more information;
- thoroughly research the topic of interest;
- gain a general understanding;
- make good use of time;
- relax;
- kill time.

Reading fosters the development of the following competencies and skills:

- 1) Lexical reading proficiency;
- 2) Grammatical proficiency;
3. Perceptual reading skills (reading technique);
- 4) the capacity to select content based on needs, interests, and desires;
- 5) the capacity to read rapidly;

- 6) the capacity to infer;
- 7) the capacity to anticipate;
- 8) the capacity to use a dictionary and other reference materials;
- 9) the capacity to comprehend the main idea and meaning;
- 10) the capacity to comprehend the text's general content; and
- 11) the capacity to identify the text's main idea.

Reading texts in a variety of genres (fiction, journalism, science, reference, etc.) helps to build these skills. [Passov,20102] Reading proficiency entails being able to rapidly connect the meaning of speech units and grammatical constructions with these units in addition to being able to read (visually identify speech units). This comprehension is predicated on the capacity to predict how specific grammatical structures and the text's meaning will be interpreted. Semantic guessing, or the capacity to deduce meaning from context for an unknown term, is also crucial. A proficient reader must not only be able to read in all genres, but also be able to switch between them with ease based on the information being obtained. They differentiate between studying (the most thorough and accurate understanding of all information contained in the text and its comprehension), viewing (reading with a general understanding, without going into details), introductory (extracting basic information from the text), and search reading (finding the necessary facts, characteristics, dates, instructions, etc. in the text quickly) based on the target setting. [Folomkina,1991]

For these kinds of readings, completely different material is chosen. It must provide pertinent and engaging material for every age group and be tailored to the communicative and cognitive needs and interests of the pupils. Working with these documents should therefore follow a distinct process. Depending on the objectives, environment, training, and other variables, a teacher will typically blend both conventional and cutting-edge technology and methodologies in practice. We prioritize communication exercises in our reading classes because they assist students learn how to work with texts of various genres and also help them build and enhance this skill.

I. Exposition (conversational in nature).

Many people enjoy taking trips and seeing to various galleries and museums.

Do you like going to galleries and museums? Why? Do you go see them frequently?

– Which gallery or museum was the last one you visited?

II. Preliminary question.

Check out some of the London tourism attractions for British visitors.

Identify the reason behind their fame.

British tourists' attractions in London	What they are famous for
The London Eye	You can enjoy beautiful works of Modern Art there.
Natural History Museum	You can learn about technological achievements there.
Madame Tussauds Museum	You can have a look at the city at the bird's-eye view.
Victoria and Albert Museum	You can see dinosaur skeletons there.
Tower of London	This place has a huge collection of arts and design.
Science Museum	This place displays the waxworks of famous and historic people and film characters.
Tate Modern	You can admire the Crown Jewels there.

III. Content identification.

Examine the ads to see if you were correct (students examine the ads to see if their selection was correct).

IV. Content search.

Examine the following list of essential terms. Identify the location of interest that each of them describes.

- a) Decorative arts and design
- b) Dinosaurs and other specimens
- c) Valuable jewels
- d) Scientific records and achievements International modern Art
- e) Wax models
- f) Breath taking view enjoy I believe, you can {admire ... at ...} learn about

V. Meaningful choice. Imagine you are in London. Where could you go if ...

- a) a) you are at Waterloo station?
- b) b) it is 9.30?
- c) c) you are fond of Science?
- d) d) want a photo with a celebrity?
- e) e) you want to see something unique and valuable?
- f) f) you are walking along the Cromwell Road?
- g) g) you want to see the collection of 4.5 million objects?

VI. The final stage of working with text (motivating students to make speech statements).

Make a top list of three tourist attractions you would like to visit and explain your choice. Follow the speech model if you need. If I were in London I would visit ..., ... and My first priority is ... because ... Then I would go to ...

because Finally, I would head for ... because ... I'm sure this would make my excursion ...

In summary, what are the benefits of utilizing technology in the teaching of reading through communicative exercises? First of all, these exercises may be used with texts of all genres and are extremely effective because of their universal nature. Second, they make frequent allusions to the material, which helps pupils comprehend it on a semantic level. Lastly, thirdly, the learner reaches a high enough reading comprehension level by completing these tasks in order, negating the requirement for open control.

REFERENCES:

1. Drozdova V.A. Functions of communication and the possibilities of their implementation in modern society // Humanitarian Research. – 2014. – No. 1 [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://human.snauka.ru/2014/01/5696> (date of access: 06/07/2018).
2. Passov E.I., Kuzovleva N.E. Foreign language lesson / – Rostov n/a: Phoenix; M.: Glossa-Press, 2010. – 640 p. – (Handbook for foreign language teachers)
3. Folomkina S.K. Some issues of teaching reading in a foreign language at a non-linguistic university // General methods of teaching foreign languages: anthology / comp. A.A. Leontyev. – M.: Rus. language, 1991.
4. Rumelhart, D. E. Understanding and summarizing brief stories. In D.La Berge & S. J. Samuels (Eds.), Basic processes in reading: Perception and comprehension. Hillsdale, N. J.: Erlbaum Associates, 1979.
5. Grabe, W., & Stoller, F. L. (2002). Teaching and Researching Reading. New York: Pearson.
6. K.M. Khabibullayevna “Implementing interactive learning technologies in developing students"communicative competence in teaching foreign languages”. *Наука, техника и образование* 86 (3), 98-100
7. Saidova, Z. U. (2024). ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 2(1), 66-70.
8. Saidova, Z. O. R. (2024). KREDIT MODUL TIZIMI ASOSIDA TALABALARNING MUSTAQIL TA'LIM KUNIKMALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI VA HAL QILISH USULLARI. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 3(2), 141-149.
9. Khasanova, G. (2023). THE ESSENCE OF SOCIO-CULTURAL ACTIVITIES AND ITS ORGANIZATIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS. *Science and innovation*, 2(B7), 92-96.